

THE USE OF OPERATIONAL-TECHNICAL MEANS IN COMBATING CRIME: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. This article analyzes legislative norms and scholarly perspectives on improving the legal and regulatory acts that authorize the use of operational-technical means. This analysis covers their application in solving the primary tasks of operational-investigative activities, conducting operational-investigative measures, formalizing their results, and enhancing the effectiveness of the operational-investigative activities of internal affairs bodies in the fight against crime. Additionally, the article addresses methodological recommendations and rules for increasing the efficiency of using operational-technical means to solve the main tasks of operational-investigative activities.

Keywords: operational-investigative activity, operational-investigative measure, operational-technical, means, procedural and non-procedural action, report, video and audio recording, cinematography and photography equipment.

Improving the legal framework for the use of operational-technical means in combating crime primarily entails aligning the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on operational-investigative activities with modern digital technologies, guarantees for the protection of individual rights, and international standards. This process is aimed at increasing the transparency of the use of modern technical means and ensuring the effectiveness of crime detection.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 3, 2025

Taking into account that the implementation of Resolution No. PQ-1 "On measures to create a safe environment in the republic's mahallas in 2025 and to further increase the efficiency of the early crime prevention system" has resulted in a nearly 1.5-fold reduction in crime in the mahallas, tasks have also been set for the implementation of an integrated system of work in this area.

In this resolution, special attention was paid to the goals and objectives of the early prevention of offenses in public places in mahallas, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies and artificial intelligence, and an electronic control system over the effectiveness of measures taken by agencies and institutions responsible for social prevention.

It was emphasized that the solution to the aforementioned problems can be found through the widespread implementation of the "My Inspector" mobile application, which allows citizens to communicate online with mahalla prevention inspectors, send photo, audio, video, and anxiety messages, as well as evaluate their activities; the implementation of the "E-conflict family" module of the "E-social prevention" information system, which allows for the collection, analysis, and monitoring of information on conflict families to prevent crimes committed within family and domestic relations; and the adoption of measures for the direct integration of the module between courts [1].

At a time when modern information technologies are developing in our country, although operational and technical means used in the activities of internal affairs bodies are the main technical means in the fight against crime, the regulatory and legal framework allowing their application has not been fully developed.

It should be noted that the legal regulation of the use of operational-technical means in operational-search activities lags somewhat behind the practice of internal affairs bodies. In the internal affairs bodies, certain shortcomings are being allowed due to the fact that certain operational officers do not know how to document the use of operational-technical means, and are unable to properly utilize their tactical and technical capabilities in solving the main tasks of operational-search activities.

In particular, although the criminal procedure law provides for the grounds and procedures for using operational-technical means, they are not given a specific name, only the activities that can be performed with the help of these means are indicated, and the methods of its application have not been developed. From theory, we know that the methods of using operational-technical means are divided into technical and tactical types.

Technical types of the use of operational technical means are not directly regulated by legislative norms. They are regulated by the general requirements and tactics of investigative activities, as well as operational-search activities. Therefore, regulatory legal acts governing this form of activity can serve as the legal basis for choosing a particular tactical method when using operational-technical means. The list of operational-technical means, their description, and operational characteristics are reflected in bylaws or may be reflected in existing technical documentation, instructions, and methodological recommendations.

The legal basis for implementing the relevant methods using operational-technical means may be legal norms (codes) or special orders.

Certain articles of the Code of Criminal Procedure regulate the use of operational-technical means and the spheres in which they must be used, as well as the system of investigative proceedings. Furthermore, the principles established in regulatory legal acts concerning operational-technical means are regulated by bylaws and serve as the legal basis for relevant instructions, rules, and other documents.

Criminal procedural legislation specifies how officials must use operational-technical means during investigations and trials, including persons conducting preliminary investigations, investigators, experts, and persons participating in investigative actions. At the same time, the law does not provide strict instructions to the investigator and persons conducting the preliminary investigation regarding the use of operational-technical means.

Article 12 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 25, 2012, No. ZRU-344 "On Operational-Search Activities" [2] establishes the right of bodies carrying out operational-search activities to conduct operational-search measures openly and covertly, to use the assistance of specialists with specialized knowledge to solve their assigned tasks, to use video and audio recording, film and photography equipment, as well as other technical means safe for human life and health, the property of legal entities and individuals, and the environment, and to create and use information systems intended for operational-search activities.

However, the use of special and other technical means (developed, adapted, programmed) intended for conducting operational-search activities and obtaining information covertly by individuals and legal entities not authorized by this law is not prohibited.

Consequently, it is advisable to include a provision in the law on operational-search activities prohibiting the use of special and other technical means by unauthorized individuals and legal entities intended for obtaining non-public information.

Referring to the experience of certain foreign countries, Part 6 of Article 6 of the Law of the Russian Federation "On Operational-Search Activity" states that "it is prohibited for individuals and legal entities not authorized by this Federal Law to carry out operational-search activities (developed, adapted, programmed), or to use special and other technical means intended for the covert acquisition of information."

Article 1 of the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Operational-Search Activity" stipulates that special technical means include devices, apparatus, tools, and equipment with special functions, software, and structural features for obtaining and documenting information during operational-search activities and covert investigative actions. There are no prohibitions on the implementation of operational-search activities, the use of special and other technical means intended (developed, adapted, programmed) by individuals and legal entities for the covert acquisition of information by these special technical means [4].

Articles 10 and 11 of the Law of the Republic of Belarus "On Operational-Search Activity" establish that the use of means for the covert acquisition (recording) of information by citizens and organizations, as well as actions not permitted by this law, is prohibited [5].

An analysis of the legislation of foreign countries shows that in some countries, individuals and legal entities are prohibited from carrying out operational-search activities (developed, adapted, programmed), using special and other technical means intended for covert obtaining of information.

The objectives of using operational-technical means in operational-search activities are:

- ensuring the protection of human rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, the property of individuals and legal entities, and the security of the individual, society, and the state;
- prevention, detection, suppression, and detection of crimes, as well as the identification and discovery of persons involved in the preparation and commission of crimes;
- conducting searches for persons hiding from bodies of inquiry, investigation, and court, evading criminal punishment, missing persons, and other persons in cases provided for by law, as well as identifying unidentified corpses;
- collecting information about individuals, events, actions (inaction) that threaten the security of the individual, society, and the state;
- use of video and audio recording, film and photography equipment, as well as other technical means safe for human life and health, the property of individuals and legal entities, and the environment;
- ensuring the safety of its employees and persons assisting bodies carrying out operational-search activities, as well as their family members, protecting their property from criminal encroachments, and others [6].

During operational-search activities, it is important to study the psychology of the perpetrator, namely:

- in making correct decisions from a criminal-legal and criminal-procedural perspective;
- selecting the most tactically optimal decisions and developing tactical combinations to resolve problematic operational situations involving suspects and accused persons;

- certain circumstances relevant to the criminal case, namely ensuring the quality of the evidentiary process, as well as the motive of the criminal act, and characterizing the identity of the suspect, accused, and victim;

- in studying the causes of a crime, taking measures for its prevention and detection (the causes of criminal aggression, the participants who committed them, and their role in the commission of the crime, etc.).

In practice, the effectiveness of operational-search measures is ensured by the comprehensive use of forces, means, and methods of operational-search activities to effectively resolve crime-fighting issues.

High efficiency in the use of operational-technical means is ensured by:

- the level of provision of internal affairs bodies with operational and technical means;
- solid knowledge of employees regarding the capabilities of specific types of operational-technical means and the practice of their application;
- awareness of the capabilities of scientific and technical means for providing operational-technical means for operational-search activities for the effective implementation of the work of the internal affairs bodies in which they serve and higher-ranking internal affairs bodies;
- knowledge of procedural rules for performing work involving operational-technical means and the documentation of the results of their use;
- continuous improvement of the professional skills of personnel using operational-technical means in the operational-search activities of internal affairs bodies;
- active interaction between operational and forensic services and units regarding the full and effective use of the scientific and technical capabilities of internal affairs bodies in accordance with the law.

In this regard, it can be noted that the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-920 dated March 13, 2024, regarding the legislation of operational-search activities, can be cited as the main directions for improving the legal framework [7].

Legislative regulation of modern technologies is a clear legal definition of the procedure for using video surveillance, biometric data, artificial intelligence and technical means of analyzing digital data, it is necessary to strengthen the mechanisms for protecting the constitutional rights of citizens, in particular, the inviolability of private life and confidentiality of information when using operational-technical means to ensure the inviolability of the person.

As we know, the digitalization of internal affairs bodies' activities, based on Resolution No. PP-5050, establishes the legal framework for using technical means to ensure public safety, integrating databases, and taking prompt measures [8].

These measures will serve to identify crimes at an early stage, strengthen the evidence base, and ensure the legality of operational-search activities.

In conclusion, it can be said that to increase the efficiency of the operational-search activities of internal affairs bodies in the fight against crime, it is advisable to improve the regulatory legal acts granting the right to use operational-technical means, educate the personnel of each system, increase their cultural, educational, and political knowledge, and take necessary measures using scientific and technical means in the fight against crime. This plays an important role in the implementation of operational-search measures for the early prevention, detection, and detection of offenses through the implementation of unified centralized electronic surveillance and monitoring using special technical means of video

surveillance installed at facilities, as well as the search for persons hiding from inquiry, investigation, and judicial authorities, evading criminal punishment, and missing persons.

Literature:

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